

E-commerce Adoption by Micro and Small Agribusiness Enterprises in Jepara, Indonesia: An Analysis Using the Technology Organisation Environment Framework

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Abstract

Background: E-commerce offers micro and small enterprises the opportunity to expand their market reach and increase profitability. However, the adoption among agribusinesses in Jepara Regency remains limited due to technological constraints and a lack of knowledge.

Objectives: This study aims to analyse the influence of technology, organisation, external environment (TOE), and trust on e-commerce adoption among micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency.

Methodology: This research was conducted in Jepara Regency, Indonesia. This study involved a sample of 100 participants, with data collected using a questionnaire. Data were analysed using SEM-PLS, applying a second-order reflective–formative model using SmartPLS 4 software. Data analysis includes instrument testing, evaluation of both measurement and structural models, and hypothesis testing.

Results: The findings of this study indicate that technological, organisational, and environmental factors have a positive impact on the adoption of e-commerce, whereas trust does not have a significant impact. Although micro and small entrepreneurs generally have a positive perception of technology, they still have concerns regarding transaction security and the reliability of digital trading partners.

Conclusion: Top management support and competitive pressure are key drivers in promoting the adoption of e-commerce. This research also reveals a new perspective, where the influence of trust may be highly contextualised, depending on the type of technology used and the user's

experience with it. The TOE framework remains relevant in explaining the adoption of technologies.

Unique contribution: This study offers insight into the factors that influence e-commerce adoption among micro and small enterprises, particularly in Jepara Regency. This research information can serve as a guideline for the government in making policies to support digital business.

Keywords: Perception of Technology; Trust; Digital Business; Key Drivers

Introduction

Micro, Small, and Medium Enterprises (MSMEs) play a role in equalising and increasing community income. MSMEs contribute to economic development through various means, such as job creation and poverty reduction (Mugano & Dorasamy, 2023). The number of MSMEs decreased in 2020 when covid-19 started. This had a significant impact on reducing cash flow and supply chain disruption.

Technological advances have driven changes in the way business activities are conducted. According to Ugwuoke and Akande (2024), digitalisation offers ease of use. Increasing business competition has compelled many entrepreneurs to adapt to the latest technologies. The most common technology used by business owners is e-commerce, as it is considered to provide numerous benefits, particularly in attracting customers.

The number of businesses utilising e-commerce in Indonesia has increased, with the largest provinces being West Java, Central Java, and East Java. The number of e-commerce users and transactions globally increased by 5 to 100% in 2020 compared to the previous year. E-commerce has transformed the way trading is conducted globally, but at varying levels. Information technology can reduce the time required for marketing products and eliminate intermediaries in the marketing chain (Rahayu et al., 2025).

Following the positive trend in major provinces such as Central Java, similar developments are also seen in Jepara Regency, with a significant increase in the number of businesses by 2023. Micro and small enterprises in the agribusiness sector in Jepara Regency have also increased significantly in 2023, including food and beverage businesses, wood processing, and organic fertiliser production. The use of digital technology is a form of adaptation in economic recovery in the new normal era, where the more optimal its utilisation, the greater the opportunity for business actors to expand the market (Riptanti et al., 2024).

Several theories, including Diffusion of Innovation (DOI), Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA), Technology Acceptance Model (TAM), and Technology, Organisation, and Environment (TOE), have been employed to explore the drivers behind e-commerce adoption. The TOE framework offers a more comprehensive perspective, not just at the individual level. The novelty in this study lies in the trust factor as an additional variable in the TOE framework. This inclusion is based on the understanding that the adoption of new technologies requires users' trust for the innovation to be effectively implemented. The TOE framework adopts an interactive approach, suggesting that organisational change is influenced not only by internal actors but also by the structural and contextual characteristics of the organisation itself (Nguyen et al., 2022). Therefore, this study aims to examine the determinants of e-commerce adoption among micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency by using the TOE

framework, with trust included as a complementary variable to provide a more holistic understanding.

Objectives/Hypotheses

Technology-Organisation-Environment (TOE)

The TOE framework states that technology, organisation, and environment are factors considered in the adoption of innovation. This theory was proposed by Tornatzky and Fleischer in 1990. The framework contains strong elements for explaining innovation acceptance at the organisational level (Katebi et al., 2022). There are five phases in the technology adoption process, namely knowledge, persuasion, decision, implementation, and confirmation (Mugano & Dorasamy, 2023). Furthermore, TOE allows for the addition of new dimensions in explaining the adoption of innovation.

Chong and Olesen (2017) conducted a meta-analysis to examine the impact and relative strength of the model. The result identified several dimensions affecting the adoption of innovative technology, including perceived benefits, top management support, competitive pressure, organisation size, and competitive pressure. The TOE framework has been widely applied to assess the adoption of innovations by organisations such as artificial intelligence (AI), e-commerce, e-business, and digital advertising.

The most influential predictors of e-commerce adoption are technological factors, specifically relative advantage and compatibility. The context represents a set of technologies available for adoption. In this research, the technology construct is measured through four dimensions, namely compatibility, complexity, relative advantage, and perceived benefits (Religia et al., 2023; Setiyani & Rostiani, 2021; Rahayu & Day, 2015). The following hypothesis is formulated to establish a structured framework.

H1: Technological factors have a positive and significant impact on the adoption of e-commerce by micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency.

Organisational readiness, in the form of effective management, is crucial to support successful adoption. The organisational context includes the resources of the enterprise, the relationship between structures among employees, the internal communication process, organisational size, and the number of backup resources. The construct is measured by top management support, organisational readiness, and cost (Religia et al., 2023; Setiyani & Rostiani, 2021; Chong & Olesen, 2017). The following hypothesis is formulated to establish a structured framework.

H2: Organisation factors have a positive and significant impact on the adoption of e-commerce by micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency.

Government support plays an important role in driving digital adoption among micro and small enterprises. The external environment serves as a critical arena in which businesses must navigate challenges and opportunities to ensure survival and growth. In this study, the environment is measured through the dimensions of government support, as well as competitive and customer pressure (Qalati et al., 2022; Setiyani & Rostiani, 2021; Chong & Olesen, 2017). The following hypothesis is formulated to establish a structured framework.

H3: External environment factors have a positive and significant impact on the adoption of e-commerce by micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency.

Trust

Trust in the context of e-commerce is considered crucial because the variable promotes risk-taking behaviour during uncertainty. Omrani et al. (2022) stated that the level of trust could affect the stoppage or abuse of technology. Trust arises from the reliability of features (service reliability) provided by an application, particularly during transaction processes. The quality of service also significantly impacts trust in using e-commerce. Hsu et al. (2014) reported that the indicators used to measure trust were security, reliability, and trustworthiness. High credibility and a strong reputation of an information technology system reflect trustworthiness. Furthermore, trust plays a crucial and beneficial role in influencing the adoption of e-commerce (Religia et al., 2023). The following hypothesis is formulated to establish a structured framework.

H4: Trust factors have a positive and significant impact on the adoption of e-commerce by micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency.

Methodology

This study adopted a quantitative explanatory design to examine the determinants of e-commerce adoption among micro and small agribusiness enterprises using the TOE framework and trust as an additional variable. Figure 1 shows the structural model of the analysis.

Fig. 1: Research Model

The population in this study consisted of micro and small agribusiness enterprises operating in Jepara Regency, Central Java, Indonesia. These enterprises were selected based on inclusion or interest in using e-commerce platforms to support business activities. Jepara Regency won

the Blangkon Jateng Award 2023 in the category of commitment to improving local MSMEs. The sample size consisted of 100 respondents, selected using purposive sampling to identify business actors engaged with e-commerce platforms such as Go-Jek, Grab, Shopee, WhatsApp Business, and Facebook Marketplace. As a complement, a snowball sampling method was applied to reach other relevant respondents who met the research criteria.

The instrument for data collection was a structured questionnaire developed based on established constructs within the TOE framework and the trust variable. The questionnaire measured multiple dimensions across five latent variables, with items rated on a five-point Likert scale. Table 1 shows the instrument development matrix of this study.

Table 1. Research instrument development matrix

Variable	Dimension/Indicator	Items
Technology (T)	Compatibility	KS1, KS2, KS3, KS4, PK1, PK2
	Complexity	K1, K2, PF1, PF2, PF3, PF4
	Relative Advantage	KP1, KP2, KP3, KP4, KN1, KN2, KN3, KN4
	Perceived benefits	EP1, EP2, EP3, EP4, MK1, MK2
Organization (O)	Top Management Support	ES1, ES2, ES3, ES4, DM1, DM2, DM3, DM4
	Organization Readiness	KA1, KA2, KA3, KA4, RP1, RP2, RP3, RP4
	Cost	BI1, BI2, BI3, BI4, BO1, BO2
External Environment (En)	Government Support	FP1, FP2, FP3, FP4, KH1, KH2
	Competitive Pressure	PB1, PB2, PB3, PB4, PS1, PS2
	Customer Pressure	KG1, KG2, KG3, KG4, PP1, PP2
Trust (Tr)	Service Reliability	KB1, KB2, KB3, KB4, KI1, KI2, KI3, KI4
	Quality Of Service	KE1, KE2, KE3, KE4, PH1, PH2
	Trustworthy	RA1, RA2, RA3, RA4, IA1, IA2
E-Commerce Adoption (AE)	Use of E-commerce in Product Sales	PE1, PE2, PE3, PE4, PJ1, PJ2
	Availability of Supporting Facilities	KL1, KL2, KJ1, KJ2
	Human Resource Readiness	KT1, KT2, KM1, KM2

Source: (Religia et al., 2023; Setiyani & Rostiani, 2021; Chong & Olesen, 2017; Hsu et al., 2014; Qalati et al., 2022; Rahayu & Day, 2015)

Before the main data collection, a pilot test was conducted with 30 respondents to evaluate the validity and reliability of the questionnaire. The results showed that several items, such as code KI1, KI4, and RA4, were invalid due to loading factors below 0.70. Therefore, the number of questions was reduced to 97 due to elimination. The final data were obtained through face-to-face interviews, recorded, and verified for consistency. Subsequently, 100 valid responses were collected and analysed using Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modelling (PLS-SEM) with SmartPLS 4 software.

The analysis was conducted using a second-order reflective–formative model, which consisted of measurement and structural evaluation. In the measurement model evaluation, the first-order reflective constructs were assessed through convergent validity (Average Variance Extracted

[AVE] and loading factors), discriminant validity (cross-loadings and the Heterotrait–Monotrait ratio [HTMT]), and reliability (composite reliability, rho_A, and Cronbach’s alpha) (Hair et al., 2019). Meanwhile, the second-order formative constructs were evaluated using outer VIF, outer weights, and outer loadings. The analysis proceeded to the evaluation of the structural model, which included assessments of inner VIF, R-squared, F-squared, and hypothesis testing (Hair et al., 2022). The mathematical model used in this research is as follows.

$$AE = \alpha + \beta_1T + \beta_2O + \beta_3En + \beta_4Tr + e (1)$$

Where *AE* is the e-commerce adoption variable, *T* is the technology variable, *O* is the organisational variable, *En* refers to the external environment variable, and *Tr* is the trust variable. β_1 , β_2 , β_3 , and β_4 are the coefficient values resulting from the analysis. In the mathematical model, *e* represents the error term, denoting the deviation between the actual values.

Results

The evaluation began with the measurement model. The results of the loading factor analysis indicated that the items KN1, MK1, MK2, and PH1 were eliminated because their loading factors were below 0.70. The analysis then proceeded to assess the reliability of the constructs, and it was found that the cross-loading, Fornell-Larcker criterion, and HTMT ratio all met the required thresholds as outlined in Hair et al. (2022). The results of the measurement model evaluation can be seen in Table 2.

Table 2. Measurement Model Evaluation

Construct	First Order				Second Order		
	AVE	Rho C	Cronbach's Alpha	Outer VIF	Outer Weight		Outer Loading
					Original Sample	P-values	
Compatibility	0.548	0.879	0.835	1.596	0.377	0.006	0.801
Complexity	0.585	0.894	0.858	1.998	0.463	0.002	0.888
Relative Advantage	0.588	0.909	0.883	2.018	0.104	0.467	0.757
Perceived Benefits	0.686	0.897	0.848	1.501	0.292	0.027	0.714
Top Management Support	0.586	0.919	0.899	1.600	0.771	0.000	0.967
Organization Readiness	0.759	0.962	0.954	1.434	0.172	0.176	0.662
Cost	0.641	0.914	0.889	1.389	0.211	0.078	0.667
Government Support	0.645	0.916	0.889	1.524	0.057	0.789	0.601
Competitive Pressure	0.663	0.922	0.898	1.284	0.725	0.000	0.906
Customer Pressure	0.660	0.921	0.897	1.409	0.429	0.073	0.721
Service Reliability	0.629	0.911	0.882	2.429	0.489	0.001	0.926
Quality of Service	0.559	0.863	0.802	2.103	0.396	0.004	0.883
Trustworthy	0.569	0.869	0.811	2.287	0.235	0.125	0.843
Use of E-commerce in Product Sales	0.608	0.903	0.871	1.764	0.663	0.000	0.946
Availability of Supporting Facilities	0.596	0.855	0.776	1.475	0.283	0.006	0.742

Human Resource Readiness	0.632	0.873	0.806	1.414	0.234	0.021	0.694
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Source: PLS-SEM Analysis

Based on the results in Table 2, the analysis of the first-order constructs was found to meet the required criteria. However, in the second-order constructs, some indicators were identified as having non-significant outer weights. Hair et al. (2022) explain that when outer weights are not significant, an analysis of outer loadings using the PLS Algorithm is necessary. The results showed that all dimensions or indicators in this study still met the threshold of 0.5 and were therefore retained (Hair et al., 2022). The analysis then proceeded with the evaluation of the structural model, which is presented in Table 3.

Table 3. Structural Model Evaluation

Construct	Inner VIF	F-square	Path	P-value
Tr → AE	2.248	0.038	0.347	0.001
En → AE	1.282	0.076	0.310	0.000
O → AE	2.124	0.141	0.177	0.027
T → AE	2.480	0.151	0.166	0.077

Source: PLS-SEM Analysis

Based on Table 3, the inner VIF values generated by the constructs were below 5 and even below 3, indicating that the values are ideal and that the estimated parameters are unbiased (Hair et al., 2022). The R-squared value obtained in this study was 0.678, indicating that technology, organisation, external environment, and trust collectively explain 67.8% of the variance in e-commerce adoption. The F-square values in this study fall into the low effect category, suggesting that there are still other variables outside the scope of this research that may help explain e-commerce adoption among micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency. The bootstrapping results showed that the trust variable did not have a significant effect at the 0.05 significance level, whereas the other variables had significant effects.

Discussion of results

Hypothesis 1 (H1) states that technology variables have a positive and significant effect on e-commerce adoption. This finding is consistent with previous studies by Tamin and Adis (2022) and Rahayu and Day (2015). Furthermore, technology is identified as the most influential variable in driving e-commerce adoption, as indicated by the highest path coefficient. Dimensions that play the most significant role in forming technology variables are complexity and compatibility. The level of complexity of a technology can be a barrier to the adoption process.

E-commerce, which is considered easy to use, encourages micro and small entrepreneurs to adopt it more readily. Based on the research results, some micro and small businesses still find it challenging to utilise e-commerce, particularly in terms of navigating foreign languages and complying with usage regulations. Entrepreneurs also perceive several advantages of e-commerce, including the ability to reach customers beyond their local areas, facilitating

customer orders, monitoring market prices, eliminating the need to rent physical storefronts, and serving as an effective promotional tool.

The relative advantage dimension exhibited an insignificant outer weight. This is likely due to many micro and small agribusiness entrepreneurs in Jepara Regency still perceiving conventional trading methods as more suitable for the current conditions. The characteristics of technology, particularly its complexity and compatibility with existing business processes and values, play a crucial role in the adoption of innovations, especially in e-commerce. Therefore, simplifying platform features and providing digital training related to e-commerce are essential steps to accelerate digital business adoption.

Hypothesis 2 (H2) states that organisational variables have a positive and significant effect on e-commerce adoption. These results align with the research of Religia et al. (2023) and Tirtana et al. (2022). The indicator that plays the most important role in forming organisational variables is top management support. The top management of micro and small businesses is typically the business owner, given their small organisational structure. Micro and small business owners in the study are mostly aged 26-35 years (in early adulthood) with an education level that mostly includes graduating from high school, allowing them to be literate in technology.

Most micro and small agribusiness entrepreneurs in Jepara Regency are technologically literate and enthusiastic about keeping up with modern market trends, making e-commerce increasingly recognised as an essential aspect of business competition. However, the dimensions of organisational readiness and cost showed insignificant outer weights in this study. Organisational readiness in terms of supporting tools can be said to be fulfilled, but this does not necessarily determine a business to adopt e-commerce. Micro and small agribusiness enterprises also said that the cost of adoption was not a major issue, and in some cases, adoption was even free of charge. However, some micro and small businesses are also burdened by administrative fees.

The results of hypothesis testing for H3 indicate that the external environment variable has a positive and significant effect on e-commerce adoption. This finding is consistent with previous studies by Paranti et al. (2024) and Religia et al. (2023). The indicators that play the most significant role in forming external environment variables are competitive pressure and customer pressure. When competitors start using e-commerce, organisations will be encouraged to adopt the technology (Rahayu & Day, 2015).

The growth of micro and small agribusinesses in Jepara Regency has created intense business competition. Many micro and small business owners in this study claimed to have customers who prefer to make purchases in person rather than use e-commerce, so conventional methods are still employed. The role of the government in promoting e-commerce adoption is perceived as insufficient by most respondents, who are predominantly street vendors and some woodcraft artisans. This explains why the outer weight of government support is very small and insignificant in this study. However, there are still some business owners who admit to receiving training from both the government and state-owned enterprises related to digitisation.

The results of the fourth hypothesis test (H4) show that the trust variable had no significant effect on e-commerce adoption. According to Gefen et al. (2003), trust may exert limited influence in contexts where users are already familiar or neutral towards a system. Various complex factors can shape trust in technology adoption (Omrani et al., 2022). In this study, many micro and small agribusiness entrepreneurs in Jepara Regency had prior experience with e-commerce, leading to a high level of response homogeneity. Consequently, trust was found to have no significant influence on the model.

Among the trust dimensions, service reliability and quality of service were the most dominant, as most respondents perceived e-commerce platforms to be reliable, easy to use, and sufficiently secure. However, the trustworthiness dimension contributed insignificantly to measuring trust. Interview findings revealed that business owners no longer compare which platform is more trustworthy; rather, they focus on whether the platform can attract customers. Some respondents reported problems, including application crashes, delayed fund disbursements, and customer support handled by AI, which often fails to resolve issues. The more reliable and trustworthy an e-commerce platform is in generating customer traffic, the more likely a business is to adopt it (Religia et al., 2023).

The findings of this study indicate that the TOE framework remains relevant in explaining the determinants of e-commerce adoption, particularly for micro and small agribusiness enterprises in Jepara Regency. Technological factors describe the characteristics of the e-commerce application itself. Organisational factors describe the internal company, which certainly affects the strength of adoption, such as top management support. In contrast, the external environment refers to the factors that influence the adoption decision, including competitive pressure. This research opens a new perspective, where the influence of trust can be highly contextual, depending on the type of technology used and the user's experience with it. Beldad et al. (2012) argued that user experience played a crucial role in building trust, particularly when the concept was positive. Although trust is not a significant determinant, it remains a context-dependent and dynamic factor. Negative experiences, such as system errors or data breaches, can decrease user trust and influence e-commerce adoption decisions. Trust may not appear critical at present, but it still warrants attention due to the evolution of conditions.

Conclusion and recommendations

This study has demonstrated that the TOE framework remains highly relevant in explaining technology adoption, particularly within the context of e-commerce. Among the variables, technology emerged as the most influential factor; when a technological solution offers high perceived benefits, aligns with business needs, and is not complex to use, micro and small agribusinesses in Jepara Regency are more likely to adopt it. The organisational dimension, particularly top management support, also significantly contributes to adoption. Furthermore, external environmental factors, such as competitive business pressures, have prompted many business owners to utilise e-commerce. Although the trust variable did not show a statistically significant effect, it still exhibited a small effect size, indicating a contextual role in influencing adoption. Overall, the effect sizes of the variables in this study were not substantial, suggesting that future research should consider expanding the theoretical model to incorporate more complex constructs in explaining e-commerce adoption.

The Jepara Regency government should implement digital training and assistance programs, especially for e-commerce, to advance micro and small businesses toward digitalisation. E-commerce application development must also ensure consistent service to build trust among both sellers and buyers. Complex models are recommended for future studies, as this one is limited to examining the indirect effects of trust. Theory development can be carried out by building an adoption phase model with stages. Therefore, research can examine the role of psychological factors, such as trust, in the long-term sustainability of e-commerce adoption.

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